

Complexes of thorium(IV) salts with morpholinomethylurea and related ligands

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Manuscript received 22 April 2002, revised 12 May 2003, accepted 17 June 2003

Complexes of thorium(IV) halides and thorium(IV) nitrate with morpholinomethylurea and related ligands have been synthesized. The studies reveal 1 : 1 complexes of thorium nitrate, thorium chloride and thorium bromide with the ligands whereas thorium iodide forms 1 : 4 complexes. The ligands are bidentate coordinating through heterocyclic N and carbonyl O (or thiocarbonyl S) in 1 : 1 complexes, whereas in 1 : 4 complexes the ligands behave as monodentate coordinating through carbonyl O or thiocarbonyl S.

Complexes of thorium(IV) with various neutral donor ligands involving Schiff bases have been reported¹⁻⁵. The preferred coordination number of thorium is 6 or 8, however higher coordination number have also been observed^{6,7}. Complexes of morpholinomethylurea and morpholinomethylthiourea with divalent transition metals viz. Co^{II} and Cu^{II} have been extensively studied in respect of their bonding, thermal and magnetic behaviour^{8,9}. The complexes of morpholinomethylurea and related ligands with rare earth metals have also been reported¹⁰⁻¹³. The present paper describes synthesis and characterization of complexes of thorium(IV) halides and thorium(IV) nitrate with morpholinomethylurea and related ligands. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, conductivity measurements, infrared and thermal studies.

Results and discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are colorless, non-hygroscopic and stable at RT. They are insoluble in water and alcohol. The behavior of complexes as non-electrolytes is indicated by their conductivity measurements. Molar conductivity $0.015-0.174 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ shows that halide and nitrate anions are bonded to thorium metal through strong non-ionizable coordinate/covalent bond.

IR spectra of the ligands morpholinomethylurea (MMU), morpholinomethylthiourea (MMTU), piperidinomethylurea (PMU) and piperidinomethylthiourea (PMTU) show sharp carbonyl absorption at 1655 (MMU) and 1660 cm^{-1} (PMU) and thiocarbonyl absorption around 1295-1310 and 770-785 cm^{-1} (MMTU, PMTU), besides, C-O-C appears at 1105 cm^{-1} . Moreover, N-H appears at 3200-3425 cm^{-1} and C-N-C in morpholine (or piperidine) ring are found at 1165 and 1140 cm^{-1} (1150 and 1120 cm^{-1}). The ligands may act as monodentate by coordinating only through its

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)	
		Th	Halide
ThCl ₄ .MMU	185	44.81 (43.51)	27.20 (26.64)
ThCl ₄ .MMTU	210	41.91 (42.25)	25.80 (25.86)
ThCl ₄ .PMU	235	43.20 (43.60)	26.00 (26.69)
ThCl ₄ .PMTU	195	42.21 (42.41)	25.52 (25.95)
ThBr ₄ .MMU	160	31.90 (32.60)	44.51 (45.00)
ThBr ₄ .MMTU	165	31.22 (31.91)	44.00 (44.01)
ThBr ₄ .PMU	204	32.47 (32.67)	45.07 (44.91)
ThBr ₄ .PMTU	200	31.92 (32.01)	43.17 (44.13)
Th(NO ₃) ₄ .MMU	233	35.39 (36.30)	-
Th(NO ₃) ₄ .MMTU	160	34.51 (35.41)	-
Th(NO ₃) ₄ .PMU	210	35.21 (36.36)	-
Th(NO ₃) ₄ .PMTU	233	35.13 (35.52)	-
ThI ₄ .MMU	200	16.32 (16.86)	36.34 (36.91)
ThI ₄ .MMTU	190	16.10 (16.11)	35.12 (35.27)
ThI ₄ .PMU	220	16.70 (16.90)	36.03 (37.02)
ThI ₄ .PMTU	192	16.72 (16.15)	34.91 (35.47)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

nitrogen donor atom or it may act as a bidentate bridging utilizing both its donor sites^{14,15}.

In the complexes of ThCl₄, ThBr₄ and Th(NO₃)₄ with ligands (MMU, MMTU, PMU and PMTU), the C=O mode at 1655-1660 cm^{-1} or C=S mode at 1295-1310 and 770-785 cm^{-1} are lowered by 20-30 cm^{-1} due to Th-O or Th-S bonding. Moreover, morpholine ring C-N-C mode of MMU and MMTU are found to be lowered indicating involvement of ring nitrogen also in coordination with metal. So, in all complexes of ThCl₄, ThBr₄ and Th(NO₃)₄ with MMU, MMTU, PMU, PMTU, ligands behave as bidentate chelating ligands.

In the complexes of ThI₄ with MMU, MMTU, PMU and PMTU, C=O mode of MMU and PMU at 1655 and 1660 cm⁻¹ are lowered to 1576 and 1630 cm⁻¹ respectively. Similarly C=S mode of MMTU and PMTU at 1295, 770 and 1310, 785 cm⁻¹ are lowered in complexes to 1192, 704 and 1202, 728 cm⁻¹ respectively. These bands indicate formation of Th-O and Th-S bonds in complexes. Further, C-N-C stretching modes of morpholine and piperidine ring are found to be same as in ligands, thereby indicating non-involvement of ring nitrogen in bonding. Thus, ligands behave as monodentate in complexes with ThI₄. This fact is also supported by stoichiometry of complexes derived from elemental analysis.

Thermal studies of two representative compounds (ThCl₄.MMU and ThBr₄.PMTU) were recorded in the temperature range of 300–973 K. The decomposition of the complexes is completed in two steps. Elimination of a molecule of urea around between 318–363 K (%wt. loss obs./calcd. = 11.26/11.46) for ThCl₄.MMU and thiourea between 323–423 K (%wt. loss obs./calcd. = 10.50/10.60) for ThBr₄.PMTU has been observed in the first step of decomposition. The second step of decomposition is attributed to the loss of N-methyl oxazime at 468–573 (%wt. loss obs./calcd. = 21.02/21.10) for ThCl₄.MMU and loss of N-methyl-2,3,4-trihydropyridine (%wt. loss obs./calcd. = 15.0/15.07) for ThBr₄.PMTU at a temperature range of 440–618 K.

Coats-Redfern method has been used for finding the kinetic parameters of complexes. The fractional wt. loss and the corresponding (1-∞)ⁿ have been calculated from TG curves at different temperatures, where 'n' depends upon the reaction model and ∞ = (w₀-w_f)/w₀-w_f. The T vs (1-∞) curves constructed on the basis of TG data for all these complexes are almost of same pattern. The weighted least-square method (LS^W) was used for obtaining best-fit linear plots by applying the data of CR method and kinetic parameters were calculated. Both the decomposition steps have been observed to follow first order kinetics as is evident from straight-line graph of -log [-log (1-∞)/T²] vs 1/T. The values of intercept, slope and activation energy were obtained from plots. The value of frequency factor (Z) and the entropy of activation (ΔS*) were calculated from the equations :

$$\text{Intercept} = \log (ZR/2E)$$

$$\Delta S^* = 2.303R \log (Zh/kT_m)$$

where *k* = Boltzmann constant, *h* the Planks constant, 2 the heating rate, *R* the molar gas constant and *T_m* the peak temperature. The *E**, *Z* and Δ*S** values are given in the Table 2.

Table 2. Thermal kinetic parameters of the complexes on the basis of CN method

Compd.	Decomp. stage/temp (K)	<i>E</i> * kJ mol ⁻¹	<i>Z</i> s ⁻¹	-Δ <i>S</i> * J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
ThCl ₄ .MMU	I/340	36.1	1728 × 10 ³	107.46
	II/520	58.0	350 × 10 ³	123.40
ThBr ₄ .PMTU	I/373	58.0	544 × 10 ³	117.70
	II/529	36.1	1773 × 10 ³	110.94

Theoretically with decreasing value of *E** the value of *Z* increases and higher values of activation energy suggest higher stability. However, there lies some inherent physical and chemical factors which may cause a change or deviation in this trend. Higher values of *E** and lower values of *Z* favors the reaction to proceed slower than normal. In present studies the numerical values of *E**, *Z* and Δ*S* altogether indicate about the smoothness of the feasibility and reaction rate of the initial reactants and intermolecular stage compounds. The negative values of entropy of activation indicate that the activated complex have a more ordered structure than the reactants or intermediates and the reactions are slower than normal. The activation energy of second step for ThCl₄.MMU is higher than the first step, which indicates that the complex ThCl₄.C₅H₉NO is more stable after loss of urea. Reverse trend is observed for ThBr₄.PMTU, where intermediate complex (ThBr₄.C₆H₁₁N) is much less stable than the original complex ThBr₄.PMTU.

Experimental

Morpholine (Fluka) and piperidine (SDS) were purified by distillation after keeping these bases over potassium hydroxide overnight. Urea (Merck), thiourea (Ranbaxy), formaldehyde (Qualigens), thorium halides (ThX₄, where X = Cl, Br and I and thorium Th(NO₃)₄ (thorium nitrate) were used as such. Ligands were prepared by reported methods⁸. For preparing complexes, thorium salt (0.005 mole) was dissolved in water (10 ml) and solution of MMU and related ligands in ethanol (15 ml) was added to it in 1 : 4 ratio. The complexes formed after 10 min were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Thorium and halogens contents were determined gravimetrically as thiourea and silver halides respectively. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO₄. C, H and N were analyzed by semi-micro combustion process. Molar conductance (in DMSO) was determined using an Elico CM 82 T instrument. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on SP 1200 and SP 2000 IR spectrophotometers. Thermogravimetric analysis was performed on a DTG-60 thermoanalyzer at a heating rate of 10°/min in static N₂ atmosphere.

Note

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